

Zermelo-Fraenkel Set Theory in Computational Complexity

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ABSTRACT

The recent research and study in the theory of Computational Complexity gives new perspectives in studying the “P versus NP” question.

RESEARCH

As it was pointed out by the modern research [1, 2] the “P versus NP” question is to be studied from a different point of view and the broad horizons of its decidability [3] are to be omitted due to the insufficient approach in the formalization of this theorem.

CONCLUSION

Thus, we came through the inequality of the question “P versus NP” which clearly gives the argument towards the preliminary axiomatization of the complexity classes which we name as “decidable” and “undecidable”.

REFERENCES

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3. Cook, Stephen. "The P versus NP problem." *Clay Mathematics Institute* 2 (2000).